

EFFECTIVE METHODS OF TEACHING READING IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE LESSONS

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Abstract: *The article discusses one of the most important aspects of learning foreign languages - reading, which is both a goal and a means of teaching.*

Keywords: *foreign languages, speech activity, reading, vocabulary, study.*

INTRODUCTION

The study of foreign languages contributes to the general speech development of students. Reading is one of the main types of speech activity. It can act as both a goal and a means of teaching. With the help of reading, a person becomes familiar with the scientific and cultural achievements of mankind, gets acquainted with the art and life of other peoples. The reading process has a huge impact on the formation of personality. With the help of reading, the active and passive vocabulary of words in students is enriched, grammatical skills are formed. Learning to read is one of the problems that received the most complete coverage in the previous stages of the development of the methodology.

METHODOLOGY

Great attention has always been paid to the problem of developing reading skills. Reading in a foreign language should be independent, carried out not under duress, but accompanied by the interest of students. However, practice shows that students' interest in reading is rather low. This type of speech activity is not always for schoolchildren the main means of obtaining information, raising the cultural level, or simply a source of pleasure. In the structure of reading as an activity, motive, purpose, conditions and result can be distinguished. The study of foreign languages contributes to the general speech development of students. Reading is one of the main types of speech activity. It can act as both a goal and a means of teaching. With the help of reading, a person becomes familiar with the scientific and cultural achievements of mankind, gets acquainted with the art and life of other peoples. The reading process has a huge impact on the formation of personality. With the help of reading, students' active and passive vocabulary is enriched, grammatical skills are formed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Foremost, the purpose of interactive learning is to improve the efficiency of the educational process, in which all students achieve high learning outcomes. Let us

consider this problem using the example of teaching students of non-linguistic universities a foreign language, in particular, English.

Interactive learning involves immersing students in a real environment of business cooperation to solve problems in order to develop the necessary qualities of a future specialist. All participants in the educational process interact with each other, exchange information, jointly solve problems and simulate the situation.

The use of interactive forms of education when working with students of nonlinguistic universities has a number of advantages, namely:

- involvement of students in the learning process no longer as listeners, but as active participants;
- increasing the motivation of this category of students to study the subject;
- mastering modern technical teaching aids;
- the formation and development of skills for independent work in the search for information and the productive use of the knowledge gained in practice.

It should be noted that the educational process with students of non-linguistic universities, based on the use of interactive technologies, aims to involve all students in the educational process, regardless of their level of language training. Collaboration means that all participants exchange information and ideas. In such a lesson, an atmosphere of free communication is created, which is characterized by cooperation between the participants in the educational process, equality of arguments, the accumulation of common knowledge, fair assessment and mutual control.

In the structure of reading as an activity, motive, purpose, conditions and result can be distinguished. The motive is always communication or communication using the printed word; the goal is to obtain information on the issue that interests the reader. The conditions of reading activity include mastering the graphic system of the language and methods of extracting information. The result of the activity is the understanding or extraction of information from the read with varying degrees of accuracy and depth. The motive is always communication or communication using the printed word; the goal is to obtain information on the issue that interests the reader. The conditions of reading activity include mastering the graphic system of the language and methods of extracting information. The result of the activity is the understanding or extraction of information from the read with varying degrees of accuracy and depth. In the process of teaching a foreign language at school, reading, like speaking, acts as an end and means: in the first case, students must master reading as a source of information; in the second - to use reading for better assimilation of linguistic and speech material.

The use of reading as a source of information creates the necessary conditions for stimulating interest in studying this subject at school, which the student can satisfy on his own, since reading does not require an interlocutor or listeners, but only a book. Mastering the ability to read in a foreign language makes it real and possible to achieve the educational, educational and developmental goals of studying this subject.

Types of reading: distinguish introductory, study, viewing and search reading. Introductory reading is cognitive reading, in which the entire speech work (book, article, story) becomes the subject of attention of the reader without the intention to receive certain information. This is reading "for oneself", without a preliminary special setting for the subsequent use or reproduction of the information received. During introductory reading, the main communicative task facing the reader is to extract the basic information contained in it as a result of a quick reading of the entire text, then there is to find out what issues and how are resolved in the text, what exactly is said in it on these issues. It requires the ability to distinguish between primary and secondary information. Studying reading provides for the most complete and accurate understanding of all information contained in the text and its critical understanding. This is a thoughtful and unhurried reading, assuming a purposeful analysis of the content of what is being read based on the linguistic and logical connections of the text.

CONCLUSION

Its task is also to form the student's ability to independently overcome difficulties in understanding a foreign language. The object of "study" in this type of reading is the information contained in the text, but not the linguistic material. It is learning reading that teaches respect for the text. Viewing reading involves getting a general idea of the material being read. Its purpose is to get the most general idea of the topic and the range of issues discussed in the text.

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